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Mitigating environmental assisted cracking in heterogeneous welds by laser peening without coating

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ABSTRACT

In this work Laser Peening without Coating (LPwC) was applied underwater on heterogeneous weld joint made of P265GH and X6CrNiTi18-10 steel tubes to prevent Environmental Assisted Cracking on the weld/P265GH steel fusion boundary. Special laser head was designed to precisely deliver 200 mJ green laser beam on the centrally located weld interface on the inner surface of a pipe 76 mm wide and 420 mm long. Residual stress analysis revealed that the LPwC treatment led to generation of compressive residual stresses in the critical fusion boundary area with the magnitude of -168 MPa despite the absence of a protective layer in the peening process. The depth of compressive stresses reached up to 0.8 mm. Plastic deformation induced by LPwC led to grain refinement in the microstructure and improved hardness by 16 %. Samples sectioned from the treated pipe were subjected to accelerated corrosion-mechanical testing which showed more than 2.5x increase in cycles to failure after LPwC. Fractography analysis showed shorter length and decreased number of corrosion cracks after LPwC as well as formation of protective oxide layer on top of the treated surface. 3-point bend testing further showed more than 8x increase in corrosion fatigue life.

1. Introduction

Heterogeneous welded connections of ferritic-pearlitic and austenitic steel are often used in construction of piping systems in both coal and nuclear power plants [1]. A typical example is the connection between the secondary loop piping system and the steam generator of water-water energetic reactor (VVER) type power plants. The combination of two different materials with various chemical and thermal properties together with exposure to high temperature corrosive environment and high tensile stresses generated by the welding process near the weld joint creates ideal conditions for corrosion cracks to develop [2]. Such welds are therefore among the critical points of power plant's piping as the operational experience has shown. In the described conditions, the main cause of failure is a localised corrosion crack propagating in, or along the fusion boundary between the weld and carbon steel. Normally, the material with lower corrosion resistance (carbon steel) is affected, but there are also less common instances of crack propagation through higher alloyed weld metal [3].

To mitigate the danger of environmental assisted cracking (EAC) related failures, several approaches can be adopted such as post-

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Fig. 1. Dissimilar tube welded in the centre.

weld heat treatment, mechanical shot peening, surface coatings, laser shock peening, etc. Laser Shock Peening (LSP) is an innovative and powerful technology that addresses the residual stress component in EAC and fatigue problematic [4]. LSP uses high-energy nanosecond laser pulses to generate shock waves, imparting deep compressive residual stresses within the material [5]. Compared to available alternatives, LSP can penetrate deeper typically up to 1 mm to 2 mm into the material, which provides a considerable shield to EAC by reducing/eliminating the tensile stresses that often lead to these failures [4,5]. LSP has gathered interest of researchers and several papers have been published in the recent past demonstrating LSP potential to mitigate SCC in weld joints.

Gong et al. [4] have studied the effects of LSP on SCC of FSW developed TC4/2A14 heterogeneous welds where they identified severe plastic deformation after LSP treatment and the grain refinement in microstructure with significant reduction in corrosion rate. Hatamleh et al. [5] studied the effect of LSP on SCC in 2195 Al alloy FSW joints and discovered that samples treated with LSP showed no evidence of pitting or SCC in a 3.5 % NaCl solution. Wang et al. [6] investigated the LSP impact on the resistance to SCC in 7075 Al alloy laser-welded joints, and found improvements of 11.13 % in elongation, 20 % in fracture time, and 100 % in static toughness. Zhou et al. [7] have studied the effect of LSP on high-cycle tension–tension fatigue performance of the 1Cr18Ni9Ti/GH1140 and identified that LSP successfully transforms the stress regime from tensile to compressive and fatigue limit improved from 289 to 478 MPa. The effects of LSP on the tensile strength and impact toughness of Inconel 625 and UNS S32205 dissimilar welds made with pulsed current tungsten arc welding was investigated by Ramkumar et al. [8]. It was discovered that residual tensile stress dominated the fusion zone of these dissimilar weldments, whereas compressive stress was created on the surface of the dissimilar weldments and extended to the depth as a result of LSP. According to Chattopadhyay et al. [9], LSP increased the fatigue strength of commercially pure titanium welded joints by 24 %. Warm LSP application on high circumferential vibration fatigue limit of gas tungsten arc welded Ti6Al4V titanium alloy was studied by Feng et al. [10] and 42.3 % increase in fatigue life was shown.

LSP can generally be applied in two ways i.e. (i) with sacrificial coating over the target material; and (ii) without any sacrificial coating. The role of the sacrificial coating is to absorb the heat generated in the laser pulse impact while the shock wave is allowed to pass through. Without the protective coating, tensile residual stresses are often generated on the material surface [11–13]. To address the issue, a specialized peening strategy was developed by Y. Sano which utilizes low pulse energy, high pulse density and second laser harmonic [14–16]. The treatment is applied underwater and was shown to generate compressive residual stresses on the material surface despite the absence of the protective layer [17]. This method is referred to as Laser Peening without Coating (LPwC). A considerable advantage of the LPwC method is that it can be easily applied on more intricate geometries, often associated with real parts, while the LSP method is often limited by more simple planar geometries suitable for application of the protective coating. The downsides of the LPwC technique is lower laser power available due to the conversion efficiency and low processing speed associated

Table 1
Chemical composition of the tube materials.

Material / Wt. %	C	Mn	Si	P	S	Ni	Cr	Ti	Cu
P265GH	0.2	1.4	1.4	0.025	0.02	0.3	0.3	–	0.3
X6CrNiTi18-10	0.08	2	1	0.045	0.015	9–12	17–19	5xC	–
SV-07Ch25N13	max. 0.1	0.8–2	max. 1	0.03	0.02	11.5–14	22–26.5	–	–

Table 2
Tensile mechanical properties of base tube materials.

Material	Temperature [°C]	Tensile strength [MPa]	Yield strength, Rp 0.2 [MPa]	Elongation [%]	Contraction [%]
P265GH	20	478	308	34	72
X6CrNiTi18-10	20	567	220	73	71

Fig. 2. LPwC treatment on the inside of welded tube: (a) LPwC mechanism, (b) schematic of developed laser head and LPwC treatment applied on the inside of a tube underwater and (c) laser head prototype used for the treatment.

with the small laser spot and high pulse density used. For practical applications, the performance can be increased by using higher repetition frequency but even then, this technique will always remain niche for specific applications related to parts with complex geometry or in difficult to reach areas.

Limited studies on improving EAC and fatigue life of the heterogeneous welds were performed with a narrow focus on laboratory samples, whereas, to exploit the full potential of the LSP method (in the present case LPwC), studies on the real-life industrial samples must follow. Thus, to explore the capabilities of LPwC, a long steel tube typically used for a secondary circuit of a nuclear power plant was chosen as a workpiece in the present work. TIG welding was used to develop the tube consisting of P265GH ferritic pearlitic steel on one side, X6CrNiTi18-10 austenitic steel on the other, and SV-07Ch25N13 as a filler material. This study includes an innovative design for treating the internal surfaces of these tubes in LPwC, focusing on important locations prone to EAC and fatigue. The outcome of the research work was evaluated by utilizing advanced characterization techniques such as X-ray diffraction for residual stresses, corrosion testing using accelerated EAC testing, and fatigue life testing using three-point bend corrosion fatigue tests. Whereas to study the deeper insights into the effects of LPwC microstructure of the samples were analyzed using scanning electron microscopy, and Kernel Average Misorientation (KAM) was also studied to infer the details of the plastic deformation.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Heterogeneous weld

Fig. 1 presents the photograph and dimensions of the tube used in the present work. It consists of two equally long steel segments of different chemical composition which are welded together. The first alloy is high carbon steel P265GH which exhibits excellent

Fig. 3. (a) LPwC strategy treatment around the weld, (b) singular LPwC patch on sectioned sample for residual stress measurements.

weldability, reliability, and durability in diverse operating conditions. It is extensively used for manufacturing tubes in power plants, particularly in boiler systems and heat exchangers. The second alloy is austenitic stainless steel X6CrNiTi18-10 also known as DIN 1.4541. It is commonly used for piping in nuclear power plants where its excellent corrosion and heat resistance make it suitable to withstand the harsh environment. The weld was made by orbital TIG method 141 welding process with filler material SV-07Ch25N13. The heterogeneous weld joint was not heat treated after welding. Chemical composition of all three alloys is presented in Table 1 and mechanical properties in Table 2. For simplicity purposes, the different steel alloys will from now on be referred to as carbon steel (P265GH), austenitic steel (X6CrNiTi18-10) and filler (SV-07Ch25N13). A total of five full welded tubes were used for the present experiments.

2.2. Laser peening without coating

A schematic of the laser peening without coatings (LPwC) process is shown in Fig. 2a. Metallic sample submerged underwater is hit by a focused nanosecond laser pulse. The pulse is absorbed, and rapidly expanding plasma is created. The expansion generates a shock wave that propagates through the sample, plastically deforming it and imparting compressive residual stresses (RS) as a result. The maximum pressure generated in the process is strongly enhanced by the confining effect of the water surrounding the impact [18]. In the present work, the second harmonic at 515 nm of Bivoj laser with top-hat square beam profile at HiLASE laser centre was used. The green laser wavelength was chosen specifically to prevent infrared laser absorption in water. In order to accurately deliver the laser beam on the inside of the welded tube, special periscopic laser head and a water tank were developed (Fig. 2c). The laser beam enters the head inside the water tank through a laser window.

During the treatment, the head including the optics was filled with water and was completely submerged in the water tank. The beam was focused through an adjustable lens inside the vertical part of the head (Fig. 2b). The tube was then attached to a robotic arm with the laser head inserted inside the tube. Combination of rotary and slowly descending motion of the tube produced spiral like peening pattern over the weld area on the inner wall of the tube (Fig. 3a and Fig. 3b). To prevent air bubble build-up on the submerged optics and treated weld area, flexible tubing was used to continuously blow the bubbles off with a stream of water. The pulse energy was 200 mJ with 10 ns pulse duration and 10 Hz repetition frequency. With spot size of 0.7 mm, the resultant power density was 4 GW/cm². The LPwC treatment was applied symmetrically in a 20 mm long strip across the weld with 3600 pulses/cm² pulse density. The length of the treated area was chosen to fully cover the 15 mm long heat affected zone (HAZ) of the weld and in particular the fusion boundary between the weld and carbon steel where the EAC cracks are most likely to develop. The time it took to treat one tube was about 5 h.

3. Characterization

3.1. Residual stress measurement

Surface RS measurements were carried out on Rigaku AutoMATE II X-ray diffractometer (XRD) using the $\sin 2\psi$ method and Cr K α (2.2897 nm) radiation. The austenitic steel was measured at Bragg peak $2\theta = 128.8^\circ$ while both the carbon steel and filler were measured at $2\theta = 155.8^\circ$. Each point was measured at 6 inclination angles with 2 mm aperture size, 30 s exposure time and 3° angular oscillation. The maximum penetration depth was estimated to be 1–2 μm . Each XRD measurement was repeated 3 times. In-depth RS measurements were acquired using the hole drilling (HD) method using the Prism device from StressTech. The drill diameter was 1.65

Fig. 4. (a) pre-cut tube and sample dimensions for EAC accelerated test and (b) pre-cut tube and sample dimensions for corrosion fatigue test.

Fig. 5. (a) sample in corrosion chamber of the EAC accelerated test and (b) sample during 3-point bend corrosion fatigue test.

mm and the drilling speed was 40000 rpm. Due to the curved geometry, the fixing force was applied in the middle of the specimen to prevent external stresses interfering with the measurement. Smaller drilling increments were taken closer to the material surface. Each hole drilling measurement was repeated twice. Surface RS were measured in both scanning (σ_S) and transversal (σ_T) directions with respect to the laser beam passing. In-depth RS were measured only in transversal direction, i.e. perpendicular to the weld, due to geometrical constraints of the curved tube section used in the HD measurement. In this configuration, transversal RS are responsible for the EAC crack propagation which runs parallel to the weld, specifically on the weld/carbon steel fusion boundary. Photographic depiction of the LPwC patch used for RS measurement is presented in Fig. 3b.

3.2. Corrosion-Mechanical testing

To examine the effects of LPwC, an accelerated corrosion-mechanical tensile test was carried out in superheated hydrogen saturated water vapor environment at atmospheric pressure and temperature of 360 °C. The test was conducted in a corrosion chamber (Fig. 4a) with an environmental control system and a Zwick Roell Kappa 100 SS-CF tensile testing system.

Samples were first statically loaded at 100 MPa for a period of 72 h. Next, the samples were subjected to constant load of 159.5 MPa superimposed with a dynamic component with amplitude of 130.5 MPa at 1 Hz loading frequency. The test was run until failure. The hydrogenated steam environment is based on a concept developed by the University of Manchester [19,20] which uses the combination of water steam and hydrogen gas to achieve oxidation effects corresponding to the corrosion cracking conditions in pressurized water reactor (PWR) environment. The samples were manufactured directly from the welded tube. First, the outer diameter of the welded tube including the weld face was machined down to lower the sample thickness. Second, dog bone shaped samples with the weld located in the centre (Fig. 4a) were pre-cut into the tube using electric discharge machine. This preserved the original enclosed

Fig. 6. Surface residual stress measurement across the welded joint before (as-built) and after the LPwC treatment.

cylindrical geometry for the LPwC treatment while at the same time avoided any post-treatment RS release in the weld area as a result of mechanical cutting in close proximity to the treated area. Once the LPwC treatment was finished, the samples were separated by cutting both their ends, far from the LPwC affected weld area. In total, 5 samples were used in the test for both the as-built and LPwC condition.

Furthermore, a corrosion fatigue 3-point bend test in demineralized water at 100 °C was performed. This test served as complementary to the accelerated EAC test and aimed to provide more insight into the material characterization and LPwC effects in terms of crack initiation and propagation. This time the mechanical loading was directly targeted at the boundary between the weld root and carbon steel. The test utilized rectangular samples which were manufactured by a process similar to the previous case, i.e. pre-cut from a machined welded tube with the weld positioned in the specimen's centre as shown in Fig. 4b. The tests were carried out on ElectroPuls E10000 fatigue machine in 3-point bend configuration with 30 mm distance between the supports. Static bending moment of 250 MPa was applied to the samples which were superimposed with dynamic component of 150 MPa at 30 Hz to shorten the time required for crack initiation. A photograph of the corrosion chamber for the EAC accelerated tensile test is presented in Fig. 5a. The heated demineralized water was delivered to the weld via silicon tubing as shown in Fig. 5b. Similar to the accelerated tensile EAC test, 5 samples were tested for the fatigue for both the as-built and LPwC condition.

3.3. Microstructure and hardness

Samples for metallography analysis were prepared by grinding and polishing extracted cross-sections of welds using SiC grind paper with progressively finer grit size followed by diamond suspension and OP-S colloidal silica suspension. The surface structures of the metallographic weld cross sections were evaluated using Keyence VKX 100 optical profilometer and Tescan Mira 3 scanning electron microscope (SEM) with energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) chemical analyser and electron back scatter diffraction (EBSD). Struers Durascan hardness tester was used for in-depth microhardness measurements from both sides of the weld up to a depth of 1.55 mm with a step of 0.1 mm between indentations.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Residual stress analysis

Surface RS measurements on the welded specimen are shown in Fig. 6. The graph is divided into several zones comprising the weld, LPwC area and HAZ with one welded material on each side. Despite being affected by the heat from the welding process, the carbon steel in as-built condition does not show significant tensile stresses. The HAZ resulting in tensile RS is more noticeable in the austenitic part of the weld where all the measurements are shifted towards positive values up to 300 MPa. Once the HAZ is passed, a decline in tensile stresses can be observed. While the LPwC treatment in both directions shows similar trends, σ_T stresses are shifted towards compression over the whole measurement area. This is a feature of the LPwC method, where the stress anisotropy can be explained by stress field interaction of highly overlapping laser pulses in a single pass peening pattern [21]. As a result, the residual stresses are higher in the advancing transversal direction as opposed to the scanning direction. The scanning strategy was chosen in such a way that the higher compression σ_T here is perpendicular to the EAC crack propagation along the carbon steel and weld fusion boundary. The newly generated compressive RS on the boundary are -168 MPa as opposed to -53 MPa before the treatment. The sudden discontinuity in stresses in the weld area can be attributed to the XRD measurement which tends to provide inaccurate results when unspecified material mixtures of the weld are being measured.

Fig. 7. In-depth residual stresses (σ_T) measured on a welded joint before (as-built) and after LPwC treatment.

The in-depth RS measured in 5 selected points of interest are shown in Fig. 7. These points are the weld centre, the fusion boundaries and the LPwC areas within the HAZ on each side. In all 5 cases, the LPwC treatment led to generation of compressive RS. Maximum compression achieved in the carbon and austenitic steels was -168 MPa and -429 MPa, respectively. The depth varied within the 0.4–0.8 mm range with the deepest compressive RS of 0.8 mm being achieved on the carbon steel and weld fusion boundary. In regular LSP, it is not uncommon to reach over 1 mm in depth, however, in this case the maximum depth is limited by the small spot size given by the low pulse energy. Pressure waves generated in small spot size tend to attenuate faster as they fall off in a radial manner $\sim 1/r^2$ as opposed to planar attenuation $\sim 1/r$ associated with larger spot sizes [22,23]. In some cases, the residual stress measured approaches or even exceeds the tensile strength of the material provided in Table 2. This is most evident in Fig. 7e in the austenitic steel area where the maximum tension recorded is more than 600 MPa. These results are likely linked to errors occurring in the hole drilling interferometric measurement arising from the spackle pattern reading. The overall trend, however, is very clear. LPwC turns tensile stresses of both as-built base materials into compressive across the whole peened area.

4.2. Microstructure and Micro hardness analysis

Prior to the LPwC treatment, the weld root topography shows typical melted structure associated with the resolidification of the weld filler material (Fig. 8a). Additionally, traces of chip machining could be observed outside the weld on the inner surface of the welded joint. Once LPwC was applied, the surface morphology changed (Fig. 8b). A thin remelted layer was created on top as a result of heat being absorbed during the laser pulse impact in the absence of protective layer. Small voids in the structure can be observed due to

Fig. 8. Typical surface topography of the weld root: (a) HAZ in the as-built condition and (b) weld root after LPwC.

Fig. 9. Oxygen concentration in the surface layer of the welded materials before and after the LPwC treatment.

gases produced by the evaporation of water being trapped by the molten metal. In addition, it was possible to observe small cavities in the HAZ region of the carbon steel, but these may not have been due to the LPwC process. Studies have shown that the remelted layer can have a positive impact on corrosion behaviour of the affected material [24–27]. The remelted layer is characterized by increased amount of oxygen, in this case around 10–15 wt% on the surface, depending on which of the welded materials was analysed, and the elements accompanying the welding process. The depth profile of the oxygen rich layer is shown in Fig. 9. The highest weight fraction of oxygen after the LPwC process could be observed for the carbon steel which reached up to 30 wt% between 1 and 2 μm in depth. In contrast to the austenitic steel, the carbon steel surface already contained some oxygen prior to the peening process which can be attributed to its lower thermal stability. An oxygen rich layer was also created on the austenitic steel peaking at 25 wt% at about 2 μm. EBSD analysis shows that the oxide layer is mainly represented by phase fraction increase of Fe_2O_3 for the carbon steel and Cr_5O_{12} for the austenitic steel. The thickness of the oxygen rich layer was between 4.5–6 μm.

Further, to understand the underlying mechanism of LPwC on the microstructure of the high carbon steel and austenitic steel, EBSD has been used to generate the inverse pole figure (IPF) and Kernel average misorientation (KAM) mapping. Fig. 10a and Fig. 10c depict IPF images of the as-built state of high carbon steel (BCC) and austenitic steel (FCC). Whereas Fig. 10b and Fig. 10d present the same for the LPwC treated. It can be noticed on comparing Fig. 10a with Fig. 10b that LPwC substantially affected the microstructure of the high-carbon steel (BCC), as it exhibits significant grain refining. In the as-built sample (Fig. 10a), a visibly large variation in the distribution of grain sizes with a coarse and elongated grain structure can be observed. Anisotropy in the grain orientation can also be seen, which could lead to develop stress concentration zones within the material. Further, after LPwC (Fig. 10b) a notable change in

Fig. 10. Inverse pole figures for (a) as-built state of carbon steel; (b) LPwC treated carbon steel; (c) as-built state of austenitic steel and (d) LPwC treated austenitic steel.

Fig. 11. Results of the EBSD analysis KAM maps comparison: (a) initial state of carbon steel; (b) LPwC of carbon steel; (c) initial state of austenitic steel; (d) LPwC of austenitic steel; and (e) details of KAM values.

Fig. 12. In depth Vickers hardness measurement of the as-built and LPwC treated samples on the inner side of the weld.

microstructure can be seen with more refined and equiaxed grains due to dynamic recrystallization effects of the LPwC processing. Similar observations can be seen on comparing Fig. 10c with Fig. 10d where LPwC effectively alters the grain sizes and orientation of the austenitic steel. The changes observed in the microstructure is in line with the results of the RS (Fig. 7) where the stresses regime has been seen changed from tensile to compressive. Furthermore, Fig. 11 compared the KAM maps. It shows higher misorientation in the crystal lattice for BCC material close to the surface after the LPwC treatment, whereas LPwC effects on FCC structure is subtle. Due to inherent ductility in FCC structure, possibility of absorbing the induced stresses is higher which may restrict the dislocation multiplication, whereas BCC structure being more brittle compared to FCC structure may push significant changes in dislocation density and grain boundaries. A more significant value of the deformation of the crystal lattice recorded by the KAM metric in the near surface region points to more significant plastic deformation occurring due to the movement of dislocations. This can be attributed to the influence of LPwC, specifically the shock waves generated in the process.

LPwC treatment enabled plastic deformation within the material which also led to nominal change in hardness of all the treated materials including the weld filler. The in-depth hardness data before and after the treatment can be seen in Fig. 12. The lowest improvement was observed in the carbon steel where only the upper most surface layer of about 500 µm was affected. The increase was roughly 16 % from 155 HV to 180 HV. A similar percentage increase was observed both for the austenitic steel and weld filler but this time across the whole measurement range of 1.5 mm. These results are in accordance with previous findings where the increase in hardness was also attributed to LSP induced plastic deformation which led to increase in dislocation density [28], grain refinement [29] and in some cases due to phase transformations [30]. It is important to note that in the present experiments no phase transformation was observed, while the change in microstructure in terms of grains redistribution, formation of new grain boundaries and increase in misorientation were observed and discussed in Fig. 10 and Fig. 11.

Fig. 13. Results of accelerated EAC test of as-built and LPwC treated samples.

Fig. 14. Sample fractography after accelerated EAC test: (a,b,c,d) as-built samples, (a) fracture starting at the interface of the weld root and austenitic steel, (b) secondary cracks developing on the opposite side of the weld root close to the carbon steel boundary, (c) side view of secondary crack close to the carbon steel boundary and (d) fracture surface. (e,f,g,h) LPwC samples, (e) fracture starting at the interface of the weld root and austenitic steel, (f) opposite side without cracks, (g) side view without secondary cracks, (h) fracture surface.

4.3. Corrosion-Mechanical testing

The results of the accelerated EAC test are shown in Fig. 13. Samples treated by LPwC have shown more than 2.5x increased resistance to the combined effect of mechanical and environmental influence. The increased life is primarily attributed to elimination/reduction in the stress concentration zone from the critical area of the weld root and austenitic steel interface and induced compressive RS by the LPwC process in that zone (Fig. 7d). Another contributing factor could be the formation of the passivation oxide layer (Fig. 9) which provides improved resistance to the chosen environment and thus increase the crack initiation time [31]. To better understand the underlying mechanism, fractography analysis of samples after the accelerated corrosion-mechanical test is presented in Fig. 14. It can be inferred that in all cases the main fracture was symmetrical and was initiated at the interface of the weld root and austenitic steel (Fig. 14a and Fig. 14e) rather than the carbon steel. The observed results can be justified with the facts that the multilayer welding process led to repeated heating of the weld root and high carbon steel interface, resulting in annealing of the structure which can be evidenced by polygonal ferrite grains and fine grain structure of high carbon steel at the root weld (Fig. 10b). The annealing effect is further supported by both the surface (Fig. 6) and in-depth RS analysis (Fig. 7b) which shows very small RS on the weld root and carbon steel interface. Such effects are more prevalent in high carbon steel which exhibits BCC structure due to its materials properties which

Fig. 15. Secondary cracks in as-built samples after accelerated EAC test: (a) secondary cracks developing in the weld close to the carbon steel boundary and (b) detail of the cracks.

Fig. 16. Results of 3-point bending test of as-built and LPwC treated samples.

tends to respond to the thermal heating and cooling cycle. In contrast, the interface of the weld and austenitic steel shows high tensile RS which leads to preferential crack initiation at the weld and austenitic steel interface. Apart from the main crack, secondary cracks were observed in the weld close to the carbon steel interface (Fig. 14b and Fig. 14c). These cracks were usually located on the sides of the test sample further away from the weld root or on the outer machined surface of the sample (Fig. 15). The location of the cracks can be explained by the previously mentioned grain refinement of the carbon steel on the inner surface which leads to higher corrosion resistance. The in-depth RS analysis in Fig. 7b and Fig. 7c further shows that the tensile stresses tend to be shifted deeper away from the surface inside the material where the secondary cracks were observed. The LPwC treated samples then showed significant reduction in the secondary cracks (Fig. 14f and Fig. 14g). Although the location of the cracks did not change, the cracks were detected only in 2 samples out of 5 and their length was significantly reduced after LPwC. In contrast, the secondary cracks were detected in all the as-built samples after the test. The obtained results correlate well with the previously published studies aimed at evaluating the corrosion resistance of welded joints. In these studies, it is stated that the increase in their resistance is associated with a refinement of the material's grain structure [32,33] and an increase in the value of the generated residual compressive stresses [34], which is related to an increase in the density of dislocations in the laser-peened surface.

Since the EAC test did not result in a crack occurring on the critical weld/carbon steel boundary, different mechanical test was performed to confirm the effect of LPwC. To focus the mechanical loading to the desired area, 3 point bending test was used. The results are shown in Fig. 16. The LPwC treated samples showed more than 8 times increase in fatigue life. It can reasonably be expected that the real improvement would be higher since only 1 out of the 5 tested LPwC samples cracked prior to test termination at 10^7 cycles. The fatigue life improvement is attributed to the deep compressive RS generated by the LPwC treatment (Fig. 7) as well as the oxygen rich remelted layer created in the treated area. The fatigue crack occurred on the interface of the weld and carbon steel which was the

Fig. 17. Sample fractography after 3-point bending test in heated water environment: (a,b) as built samples and (c,d,e,f) LPwC samples, (a,c) top view of corrosion fatigue crack on the weld and carbon steel interface at the weld root, (b,d) side view of the crack with corrosion damage on the carbon steel surface, (e) SEM of the fatigue crack with corrosion pits visible and (f) detail of the crack tip.

location of maximum loading (Fig. 17a and Fig. 17c). The crack propagated perpendicular to the direction of loading. Furthermore, extensive corrosion damage was observed on the carbon steel part of the sample (Fig. 17d) which upon closer examination was identified as corrosion pits (Fig. 17e). The damage mechanism in the test was therefore identified as corrosion fatigue and there were no significant differences in the crack morphology before and after the treatment.

5. Conclusion

In this paper, the effect of Laser Peening without Coating on heterogeneous welds frequently affected by EAC was investigated. The treatment was applied from the inside of a tube which was made of two kinds of steel – one austenitic (X6CrNiTi18-10) and one carbon (P265GH) based which is typically used in a secondary circuit of nuclear power plant piping. In this kind of tube, EAC crack is most likely to develop on the weld/carbon steel fusion boundary. Based on the results acquired using various techniques, the following conclusions can be made:

1. LPwC treatment was successfully applied on the inner side of narrow welded pipe through specially engineered underwater laser head.
2. The treatment introduced compressive residual stresses perpendicular to the weld fusion boundaries up to a depth of 0.8 mm. The magnitude of the residual stresses varied based on the different steels being affected. The surface and simultaneously maximum RS generated on the weld-carbon steel interface were -168 MPa. The surface RS on the weld-austenitic steel boundary was -97 MPa with maximum of -429 MPa about 50 μm deep.
3. A rich oxygen layer about $4.5\text{--}6$ μm thick was created on top of the treated area as a result of heat transfer taking place during the laser pulse absorption when no protective coating is used. The results suggest that this layer has positive impact on the corrosion resistance of the underlying material.
4. Microstructure has shown significant improvement as the grain size was decreased and the grain orientation has been shifted.

5. Both the carbon steel and austenitic steel showed higher dislocation density as a result of the plastic deformation taking place during the LPwC process. This led to about 16 % increase in hardness which went deeper for the austenitic steel.
6. The accelerated EAC test showed about 2.5x increased life for the LPwC treated samples. Although the main crack always occurred on the weld/austenitic steel boundary, it was also observed that the treatment had positive impact on the secondary cracks occurring in the weld close to the carbon steel. The abundance of the corrosion cracks was lowered, and their length was reduced.
7. The 3-point bending test showed more than 8x improvement in corrosion fatigue life after the LPwC treatment. The cracking occurred on the weld-carbon steel fusion boundary and the results were attributed to the compressive RS introduced by the treatment.

It is important to note that the research carried out in this paper was done in accelerated testing environment. Further steps would therefore involve autoclave testing of samples followed by testing of treated tubes in real service environment. Nevertheless, this work provides a practical way for treatment in hard-to-reach area inside of a narrow tube and the potential benefit of LPwC on heterogeneous welds in real piping parts is evident.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jan Kaufman: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **David Bricín:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Zbyněk Špirit:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology. **Josef Strejcius:** Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition. **Jan Šmaus:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Sunil Pathak:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision. **Zdeněk Fulín:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Jan Brajer:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Tomáš Mocek:** Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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